

Two new *Thecaphora* species, *T. ulicis* and *T. hosackiae* (*Ustilaginomycetes*) on *Fabaceae*

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Abstract. Two new *Thecaphora* species, *T. ulicis* on *Ulex minor* from England, and *T. hosackiae* on *Hosackia parviflora* from the U.S.A., are described.

Key words: *Fabaceae*, *Hosackia*, new species, smut fungi, *Thecaphora*, *T. hosackiae*, *T. ulicis*, *Ulex*

Introduction

The genus *Thecaphora* Fingerh. emend. Vánky (fam. *Glomosporiaceae* Cif., order *Urocystidales* R. Bauer & Oberw., class *Ustilaginomycetes* R. Bauer, Oberw. & Vánky) has 59 species parasitising dicotyledonous plants in 15 families. The *Thecaphora* species on *Fabaceae* were studied by Mayor (1947) and Vánky (1991). At present, the following 12 species are recognised on hosts in the *Fabaceae*: 1. *T. affinis* W.G. Schneid. ex A.A. Fisch. Waldh., on *Astragalus*; 2. *T. deformans* Durieu & Mont. ex Tul. & C. Tul., on *Medicago*; 3. *T. desmodii* (Peck) Woronin, on *Desmodium*; 4. *T. frezzii* Carranza & J.C. Lindq., on *Arachis*; 5. *T. hedsari* Vánky, on *Hedysarum*; 6. *T. lathyri* J.G. Kühn, on *Lathyrus*; 7. *T. loti* Mayor, on *Lotus*; 8. *T. lupini* Mayor, on *Lupinus*; 9. *T. oxytropis* S.R. Wang, on *Oxytropis*; 10. *T. sphaerophysae* Z.Y. Zhao & Y.W. Xi, on *Sphaerophysa*; 11. *T. trigonellae* Schwarzman, on *Trigonella*; and 12. *T. viciae* Bubák, on *Vicia*. A further species, *T. genistae-tinctoriae* Maublanc (1937: 124; nom. nud.) was collected in France (Dépt. Loire-Atlantique, Birochère near Pornic) but it was lost before it was described and validly published. This enumeration appears to show that each *Thecaphora* species on *Fabaceae* is restricted to host plants in a particular genus.

Margaret A. Brett (1940, 1949, 1966) collected and investigated a *Thecaphora* species on *Ulex minor* from England, identifying it as *T. deformans*. The name *T. deformans* was

earlier applied to several *Thecaphora* species on *Fabaceae*. The smut on *Ulex minor* differs from the type of *T. deformans* and other *Thecaphora* species on *Fabaceae*, and is described below as a new species.

A *Thecaphora* species was collected by C.V. Piper on *Hosackia parviflora* in the U.S.A., on 24 Jul 1895. It is preserved in BPI, once under *Sorosporium hosackiae* Piper (BPI 199209), which is a herbarium name, and once under the name *Thecaphora deformans* (BPI 179208). A study of this smut and comparison with other *Thecaphora* species on *Fabaceae* revealed that it can be considered a new species.

Materials and Methods

Sorus structure, spore ball, spore and conidia characteristics were studied using dried herbarium specimens. For light microscopy (LM) spore balls and conidia were suspended in a small droplet of lactophenol, respectively in lactophenol with cotton blue, covered with a cover glass, gently heated to boiling point to rehydrate the spores and conidia, and to eliminate air bubbles from the preparation, and studied at 1000× magnification. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), spores and conidia were placed on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, c. 20 nm, and examined in a SEM at 10 kV.

Results

Comparative studies showed that the *Thecaphora* on *Ulex minor* and that on *Hosackia parviflora* represent two new species, which are described below.

Thecaphora ulicis Vánky, sp. nov.

Mycobank: 512374

Typus in matrice *Ulex minor* Roth, England, Dorset, Wareham, Heath, 50°43'22" N, 2°06'54" W, V.1961, leg. M.A. Brett.

Holotypus in K(M) 107486! *Anamorph* on *Ulex minor*, England, Dorset, S of Wareham, Stoborough Heath, 18.VIII.1962, leg. M.A. Brett & R.W.G. Dennis, K(M) 157597!

Sori semina destruentes, leguminas massa glomerulorum sporarum brunnea, granuloso-pulverea implentes. *Glomeruli sporarum* permanentes, globosi, subglobosi, ovoidei, late ellipsoidales vel parum irregulares, (25–) 30–60 × 30–70 μm, flavido- usque purpurascens brunnei, e (3–) 7–30? sporis pressu valido non separabilibus compositi. *Sporae* in visu superficiali subangulariter circulares, ellipsoidales vel irregulares, 6,5–15 × 8–22,5 μm, in visu mediano subcuneiformes vel parum deplanatae, cum lateribus duobus deplanatis, magis raro ellipticis vel circularibus, cum latere uno deplanato, radialiter 9,5–24 μm longae, flavido-brunneae usque purpurascens brunneae; pariete in lateribus contactis cca. 0,5 μm crasso, levi, in latere libero 1–5 μm crasso, verrucis usque ad 4 μm altis, cylindricis, obtusis vel subacutis inclusis. *Verrucae* maxime altae versus centrum parietis liberi circum porum germinationis circulaem, 2–3 (–4) μm latum, levem. *Anamorpha* in antheris praesens.

Sori (Fig. 1) in one or several seeds of apparently normal or slightly deformed pods, transforming them partially or totally into a rusty brown to deep chocolate brown, semiagglutinated to granular powdery mass of spore balls. Infected seeds may also appear healthy. Infection is a floral one through the stigmata by germinating conidiospores. It may result in a local infection of the seeds only or in a systemic infection. In this case the plants will be more or less stunted. **Spore balls** (Figs 2–3) permanent, globose, subglobose, ovoid, broadly ellipsoidal or slightly irregular, (25–) 30–60 × 30–70 μm, yellowish to reddish brown, composed of (3–) 7–30? spores which do not separate by hard pressure. **Spores** (Figs 2–3) in surface view subangularly circular, ellipsoidal, elongated or irregular, 6,5–15 × 8–22,5 μm, in median view subcuneiform or somewhat flattened, with two flattened sides, more rarely elliptic or circular with one flattened side, radially 9,5–24 μm long, yellowish- to reddish brown; wall on the contact sides c. 0,5 μm thick, smooth, on the free side 1–5 μm thick, including the up to 4 μm high cylindrical, blunt or subacute warts. The warts are highest towards the centre of the free surface, around a circular, 2–3 (–4) μm wide, smooth germ pore. **Spore germination** (Brett, 1966) results in a rounded protuberance from which a 6–7 μm wide, septate, branching, filament arises. After fusion of two cells of this filament (basidium?), thinner (2,5–3 μm wide), branching, septate “fusion” hyphae develop, some of which produce “delicate terminal conidia”. **Anamorph** present in the anthers of

Fig. 1. *Thecaphora ulicis* on *Ulex minor*. A flowering shoot and a flower of *Ulex minor* with anamorph in the hidden anthers. Two opened pods with infected seeds, and three removed infected seeds (type). Bars = 1 cm

infected flowers. Conidia (Figs 4–5) varying in shape and size, globose, ovoid, ellipsoidal to elongated, globose or subglobose conidia 2–6,5 μm in diam., elongated up to 6,5 μm wide and 14 μm long, hyaline; wall 0,3–0,5 μm thick, in LM smooth, in SEM sparsely verruculose.

On *Fabaceae*: *Ulex minor* Roth.

Distribution: Several places in southern England.

Brett (1966) studied the biology of this smut in detail. According to her, the fungus may produce dwarfing of the host plants, depending on whether infection is local or systemic. Infection is initiated by conidia that develop in the anthers of infected flowers, replacing the pollen. The conidia are transported by pollinating insects to the stigmata of healthy flowers, where they germinate and infect the ovaries through the funiculus. Infection takes place during the long flowering period of *Ulex minor*, from July to October. Infected seeds develop during March to June of

Figs 2-5. Spore balls, spores and conidia of *Thecaphora ulicis* on *Ulex minor* (type). Figs 2-3. Spore balls and spores in LM and in SEM. Note the presence of germ pores as bright, rounded areas on the free spore walls on the LM picture. Figs 4-5. Conidia in LM (in lactophenol with cotton blue) and in SEM. Bars = 10 μ m

the following year. One or several seeds may be infected and destroyed partially or totally in the pods containing 2-5 seeds each. Before the pods burst, infected seeds are the same size and appearance as the healthy ones. Brett (1966) found that best spore germination was obtained with freshly collected material, although the percentage of germinated spores and the time necessary for germination was very variable. Conidia, produced on the top of the branching, septate, "fusion" hyphae (born from spore germination) are stalked, first ovoid, then pear-shaped, and finally elongated (35-40 μ m), broadest near the base (6 μ m), from which they taper

gradually to the apex and abruptly to the stalk. Conidia in the anthers of infected flowers are white in mass, hyaline under the microscope. They are ovoid and bud laterally (not apically), two or three buds often appearing simultaneously. Two conidia may fuse forming a semi-erect, terminal conidium on a short hypha, like those formed on "fusion hyphae". These germinated at once forming a hypha of 2-3 μ m diam. with multiple clamp-connections and formation of semi-upright conidia. In culture, with time, production of conidia ceased, lateral hyphal branches become coiled and spore balls start to form.

Thecaphora ulicis differs from *T. deformans* (type on *Medicago tribuloides* Lam., Algeria) by the normal or only slightly deformed infected pods, by longer spore balls (30-70 μm) composed of more spores ((3-) 7-30?), by shorter warts (1-4 μm), by the presence of an evident germ pore, presence of an anamorph in the anthers, and by the host plant genus. In *T. deformans* the infected pods are swollen, deformed, the spore balls are 24-52 μm long, composed of (2-) 4-13 spores, the warts are 1-5 (-6) μm long, germ pore and anamorph are absent. The reported "anamorph" in the anthers of *Trifolium* spp. is *Botrytis anthophila* Bond. (Vánky 1985: 124), and is not related to *Thecaphora*.

The smut fungus on *Hosackia* is described as:

Thecaphora hosackiae Vánky, sp. nov.

Mycobank: 512375

Typus in matrice *Hosackia parviflora* Benth., USA, Washington, Kitsap Co, Orchard Point, 24.VII.1895, C.V. Piper. **Holotypus** in BPI 179209! **Isotypi** in Piper, *Fungi of Washington* 474 (as *Thecaphora deformans*), BPI 179208, HUV 13616!

Sori in omnibus leguminibus abbreviatis et aliquantum tumidis plantae infectae semina destruentes et legumina massa glomerulorum sporarum ferrugineo-brunnea, granuloso-pulverea implentes. **Glomeruli sporarum** permanentes, globosi, subglobosi, ellipsoidales vel parum irregulares, raro elongati, 25-40 \times 25-45 (-55) μm , flavido-brunnei, e 3-12 (-15) sporis pressu valido non separabilibus compositi. **Sporae** in visu superficiali subangulariter circulares, elongatae vel irregulares, 8-14,5 \times 10,5-24 μm , in visu mediano subcuneiformes cum lateribus duobus deplanatis, vel ellipticae cum latere uno deplanato, radialiter 10,5-20 μm longae, flavido-brunneae; pariete in lateribus contactis 0,5-0,8 (-1) μm crasso, levi, in latere libero 2,5-4 μm crasso, verrucis 1,5-2,5 (-3) μm altis, cum apice rotundato vel subapiculato inclusis. **Verrucae** maxime altae versus centrum superficiae liberae circum porum germinationis circulaem, diametro 3-4 μm , levem. **Anamorph**a non cognita.

Sori (Fig. 6) in all, much shortened and somewhat swollen pods of an infected plant destroying the seeds and filling the pods with a rusty brown, granular powdery mass of spore balls. **Spore balls** (Figs 7-8) permanent, globose, subglobose, ellipsoidal or slightly irregular, rarely elongated, 25-40 \times 25-45 (-55) μm , yellowish brown, composed of 3-12 (-15) spores which do not separate by hard pressure. **Spores** (Figs 7-8) in surface view subangularly circular, elongated or irregular, 8-14.5 \times 10.5-24 μm , in median view subcuneiform with two flattened sides, or elliptic with one flattened side, radially 10.5-20 μm long, yellowish brown; wall on the contact sides 0.5-0.8 (-1) μm thick, smooth, on the free side 2.5-4 μm thick, including the 1.5-2.5 (-3) μm high warts with rounded or subacute tip. The warts are highest towards the centre of the free surface, around a circular, 3-4 μm wide, smooth germ pore, visible only in rehydrated spores. **Anamorph** not known.

On *Fabaceae*: *Hosackia parviflora* Benth. (*Lotus micranthus* Benth.)

Distribution: U.S.A. Known only from the type locality.

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Fig. 6. *Thecaphora hosackiae* on *Hosackia parviflora*, habit. To the left a healthy, flowering shoot (from the internet), to the right an old shoot with infected pods (type). Bar = 1 cm

Host plant identity of *Thecaphora hosackiae* on the infected specimens at hand could not be verified. In several North American floras *Hosackia parviflora* is treated under its synonym *Lotus micranthus* Benth. Mayor (1949: 58) described *Thecaphora loti* Mayor on *Lotus* sp. (= *L. humistratus* Greene), from the U.S.A. The types of these two species were compared to exclude conspecificity. *T. hosackiae* differs from *T. loti* especially by much shortened infected pods, by spore balls composed of less spores (3-12 (-15)), by shorter warts (1.5-2.5 (-3) μm), by presence of an evident germ pore, and by the host plant genus. In *T. loti* the infected pods seem to be only slightly deformed, the spore balls are composed of (3-) 5-16 (or more?) spores, the warts are 2.5-5.5 μm long, and a germ pore is absent. *T. hosackiae* differs also from *T. ulicis* in producing much shortened pods, in smaller spore balls composed of less spores, in shorter warts, in the absence of an anamorph and in host plant genus. The main differences between the types of *Thecaphora deformans*, *T. ulicis*, *T. hosackiae* and *T. loti* are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The main differences between *Thecaphora deformans*, *T. ulicis*, *T. hosackiae* and *T. loti*

Species	Sori	Spore balls	Warts	Germ pore	Anamorph	Host genus
<i>T. deformans</i>	Pods swollen, deformed	24-52 µm long, of (2-) 4-13 spores	1-5 (-6) µm high	absent	absent	<i>Medicago</i>
<i>T. ulicis</i>	Pods normal or slightly deformed	30-70 µm long, of (3-) 7-30? spores	1-4 µm high	present	present	<i>Ulex</i>
<i>T. hosackiae</i>	Pods swollen, much shortened	25-45 (-55) µm long, of 3-12 (-15) spores	1.5-2.5 (-3) µm high	present	absent?	<i>Hosackia</i>
<i>T. loti</i>	Pods slightly deformed?	30-50 (-55) µm long, of (3-) 5-16 or more? spores	2.5-5.5 µm high	absent	absent?	<i>Lotus</i>

Figs 7-8. Spore balls and spores of *Thecaphora hosackiae* on *Hosackia parviflora* in LM and in SEM (type). Note the presence of germ pores on the LM picture. Bars = 10 µm

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